

The United States Priorities Towards India: What it Means for Pakistan

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Abstract

The growing India-US strategic partnership is becoming a grave concern for South Asian countries in general and Pakistan in particular. After the September 11, 2001, incident, the Indo-US nexus has drawn the attention of academic scholars, strategic analysts, and the media. However, this deepening partnership entails serious implications for Pakistan. This study seeks to identify US priorities toward India and their implications for Pakistan. Based on the qualitative research, this article finds that the US objective is to contain China, keep an eye on Pakistani nukes, counter terrorism, and avert nuclear conflict between India and Pakistan. Consequently, America finds a big market, cheap labor, huge investment, and high-tech exchanges in India. This study relies on the Security Dilemma Theory of International Relations, in which a poor country fears the powerful state, and out of this fear it develops its security and partnerships with other countries in the region. This study suggests that Pakistan should develop strategic, political, and economic ties with China in order to balance the Indo-US strategic partnership; it ought not to rely on a single country, but instead, it should foster strong ties with other countries like Russia, China, the US, Middle Eastern countries, and neighboring states.

Key words: India, United States, Pakistan, Strategic relations, Implications, Security, Dilemma

Introduction

Since its invasion of Afghanistan in 2001, the United States began to forge close and friendly relations with India. Perceiving India as rising economic and political power, the United States started developing strong strategic ties with the former to protect and promote its interests in the South Asia region. Moreover, the growing number of militant groups and the rising influence of Communist China in the region were the major concerns of the US in the South Asia. In addition, curbing the nuclear proliferation in the South Asia region and preventing war between two nuclear states of the region i-e, India and Pakistan (Kronstadt

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& Pinto, 2013). Thus, containing the increasing influence of China, Nuclear Non-proliferation, and the soaring number of militant groups became an integral part of American's, South Asia policy. The United States found India as the most reliable partner with whose help it can attain its regional goals. While, the US has been treating India distinctively and their bilateral ties have evolved gradually.

India and America signed a defense agreement in 2005, in a bid to enhance mutual cooperation, collaboration and to strengthen bilateral defense trade and set up a bilateral "Defense Procurement and Production Group". Similarly, the two countries signed the Maritime Security Cooperation Agreement that enabled both to cooperate and to ensure the free and safe flow of trade and to counter threats to maritime security in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR). The huge amount of oil passes through these routes to fulfill the requirements and needs of China, second largest economy of the world (Owais, 2020). As a result of it, India and the United States started extraordinary joint military exercises and engaged in mutual security relationships based on shared geopolitical interests in the region. Likewise, the Civil Nuclear deal signed during the Bush era brought both countries came closer to each other. In addition to it, the QUAD (Quadrilateral Security Dialogue), which was initially formed in 2007, was revived in November 2017. The QUAD aims at promoting free and open Indo-Pacific region amid China's hostile attitude in the region.

Basically, the QUAD is based on four dimensions of power - diplomacy, information, military and economy (DIME). Similarly, it finds its common ground for policy coordination among the member counties of QUAD and counter China in the Asia Pacific region (Khalid, 2020). The United States has been shielding India's regional and international interests. Moreover, Barack Obama, during his official visit to India in 2010, supported Indian demand for a permanent seat in Security Council with five veto powers. (Asma, 2020).

The qualitative research was applied for this study where the primary and secondary methods were used for data collection. For primary data, 15 academicians from different universities of Pakistan were interviewed. While 7 out of the 15 interviews were excluded due to repetitions of ideas and information. Questionnaire was sent to experts via email. Thus, online interviews were conducted through email. Besides, purposive method of sampling was used. Whereas, the secondary data is amassed from books, articles, magazines etc. Moreover, the researcher has adopted security dilemma theory of International Relations because it would be helpful to assess the strategic partnership between New Delhi and Washington and explore the impacts of this partnership on Pakistan. The Security Dilemma theory is a condition in which a country strengthen its own security which invites response from other nations.

Literature Review

There is ample research available on India-US relations and every writer has his own point of view regarding the nexuses and its implications on South Asia region in general and on Pakistan in particular. Asma Iqbal in her study (2020) describes that conflictual relations of India and Pakistan has caused development of triangular ties among the United States, India,

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and Pakistan. While Syed Nouman Ali Shah and Dr. Gulshan Majeed's research article (2020) gives detailed account of the changing the United States priorities in South Asia region and problematic relations between the United States and Pakistan. Moreover, Shreya Upadhyay in his study (2014) outlines the United States priorities in Indo-Pacific Ocean. The United States wants to maintain its influence in the ocean as it serves former's economic and strategic interests. Interestingly, Daniel S. Markey in his book, (2013) retains the view that Pak-US relations are based on mutual vulnerability each having capability to threaten other's interests despite of difference of power wealth, culture, and history.

Further, K. Alan Kronstadt and Sonia Pinto (2013) retained view that with the US engagement in Indo-Pacific India's economic and military capabilities increase. The leading aspects of Indo-US ties include military-to-military ties, defense trade, and counterterrorism and intelligence cooperation. As suggested in the above brief literature, it showed that research has focused more on American Indo-Pacific region than India-America relations. However, these studies ignore the comprehensive analysis of major developments in Indo-US relations since the last decade and its impacts on Pakistan's security has been neglected field. Therefore, this research study has analyzed the nature of relations between the United States and India and explored their mutual interests and its impact on Pakistan.

The United States' Priorities towards India

After 9/11 incident South Asia region became center of attention of America's foreign policy makers. The United States got engaged in the region in order to protect and promote its multiple interests. In the following section, the researcher presents a various themes generated through atlas.t test. In this diagram, the researcher has tried to show how Washington has inclined its interests towards India and how American tilt towards India is concerning Pakistan or upsets the balance of power in the region and how it might further complicates Pakistan's relationship with America. American pivot to Asia and its core interests could be affected if it relies on the single country in the region while ignoring the middle powers in the region. The following diagram shows how US-India relationship are growing which could ring an alarming bells for the security and interests of the countries in the region.

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Diagram 1

Note: This diagram was developed by the author through Atlas.t software

America policy makers fear that “dramatic increase in Chinese power, it may begin to question the equity of the prevailing international order, openly challenging the United States for leadership.” (Kearn, 2014). Besides, China considers South Asia region as it’s near abroad and has launched some major economic initiatives in order to connect itself with near abroad. Therefore, containing the China has been major goal of American policy makers. “The US is inclined to India as it wants to develop strategic ties with neighbor of China.” (Khushboo, interview, 13-09-2021). The United States, with the help of India’s blue water navy, wants to protect and promote its interests in Indian Ocean and Persian Gulf. The United States considers India’s military strength as countervailing power against China. Therefore, the United States developed strong strategic ties with India. “President Obama’s support to India’s inclusion in the UN security council is also an important manifestation of the high priority that the Obama administration attaches to India.” (Bishoyi, 2011). In addition, the potential revival of Russia is considered as threat to American interests. The United States fears that it could alter or even deteriorate the international security arrangements. Moscow would get involved not only in the affairs of the Europe but also in the Middle East and Asia-

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Pacific regions. Coupled with that growing strategic cooperation between China and Russia is considered by the United States as alarming development. It could disturb the strategic equation in West Pacific. In order to contain Russia's influence in Asia-Pacific and counter the emerging Sino-Russia strategic cooperation, the United States fostered strategic ties with India.

Countering terrorism has been one of major objective of the United States engagement in the South Asia region since 9/11. The United States has never been satisfied with Pakistan's role in War on Terror. The US kept crying "do more". Moreover, the Pakistan's good Taliban and bad Taliban policy also annoyed the United States. Besides, Pakistan was accused of providing safe heavens to the Taliban. Thus, the trust deficit gave India an opportunity to become America's ally in its war on terrorism in Afghanistan. The United also wanted India's help in Afghanistan. It assigned India key role in Afghanistan. The United States gave India contract to train Afghan military. Not only that, but India was granted contract to build infrastructure in Afghanistan.

Moreover, India's biggest market coupled with cheapest source of labor for the US tech giant's investments has been major factor behind United States' inclination towards India. "The US realizes that India is too big an economy to be ignored and both countries realize that stable India-US relations are a strategic requirement which neither can afford to ignore." (Konwer, 2020). Therefore, Washington has always aspired to create smooth and favorable environment for its heavy investments in India and Indo-Pacific zone. In addition, India has been one of the major importers of the American arms. Thus, economic interests prompted the United States to develop close relations with India. "United States prioritize India for mainly two reasons which are, economic and politics. Economically, India is a big market for U.S. products that include from food items to weapons. Politically, India is largest democracy, and both have same contesters in the region that is China." (G. Ali, interview 16-09-2021). In addition, the United States assumed the role of an observer of nuclear programs of India and Pakistan. The security of India and Pakistan's, particularly of latter's, nuclear assets have been major cause of its engagement in the region. Because nuclear enmity between the two neighbors can have adverse impacts on the region and beyond. Therefore, deterring a nuclear confrontation in between two nuclear countries was one of the prime concerns of the United States. Washington has been striving to "reduce the chances of military crises between India and Pakistan." (Mistry, 2019). "Various regional and international developments changed America's policy towards India. Terrorism, security of nuclear assets of India and Pakistan, China's growing influence and India's big market forced the US to develop strong ties with India." (B. Singh, interview 18-09-2021).

Foreign policy makers of America are very much aware about the importance of India for the United States as she occupies the strategic location connecting India and Pacific Oceans. Thus, in order to get access to energy resources of the Gulf region, Middle East and South Asia, the United States has enhanced its bilateral ties with India. Moreover, the United States has strengthened its presence in the area by occupying the base facilities. The United States presence in the region aims at ensuring the freedom of trade and containing rising influence in the region. India facilitates the United States in Indian Ocean by providing its bases to

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American military. Thus, the United States is engaged in Indian Ocean in order to protect its economic and strategic interests.

What it means for Pakistan?

The growing strategic partnership between India and the United States has deeply impacted Pakistan. These implications are wide and deep. The following diagram shows how American tilt towards India could complicate its ties with middle powers like Pakistan in the South Asian region. History shows that America has been deeply engaged in South Asian region since long time. This engagement has been because of two reasons: Chinese growing influence and Afghanistan. However, increasing strategic partnership between US and India is considered as a bad omen for the peace, security, and stability of the region. In fact, it would shift the balance of power and could push further American old allies like Pakistan to look towards other powers in the region.

Diagram 2

This diagram was developed by the author through Atlas.t

Soon after the end of the Cold War, America reshaped its South Asia foreign policy. With the transformation of the U.S. foreign policy about India, the strategic relations between the two countries began to flourish. United States' post 9/11 approach towards India and its strategic ties with South Asia's biggest state was not the outcome of sudden development. In effect, the revision of the policy was the result of the sluggish convergence of interests of the two countries. "Pakistan used to be biggest non-NATO ally of the United States against the Global War on Terror (GWOT), but with the emergence of China as a competing power challenging the US status of being a superpower has changed the security apparatus of the US from Pakistan towards India as the later serves United States countering China in the Indo-Pacific."

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(Ayesha, interview on 22-09-2021).

The United States perceives India strategically, politically, and economically more important than Pakistan as former can protect its prime interests and objectives in the in the region. Bush and Obama administration indicated that their partnership with Pakistan was limited to war against terrorism whereas its cooperation with India was based on long term cooperation in commerce, trade, defense, and high-technology transfer. In this regard, the United States took number of initiatives to foster strategic ties with India. As a result, the strategic ties with the US and its support on the international forums has encouraged India to “pursue an aggressive policy towards Pakistan.” (Kaura, 2020). In addition, the defense cooperation with the United States helped India to increase its military dominancy.

Soon after the 9/11 incident, America lifted many technical sanctions against India which were imposed by the former in 1998. Besides, many the United States firms (which previously were prohibited to cooperate with India) were allowed to collaborate with India. Within years their bilateral became as strong as mountains. The United States not only opened the doors of advanced weapons and modern technology for India but also encouraged other states, including Israel, to follow the suit. India had been world’s largest arm importer for nearly a decade. Previously, military, and political support of the United States encourages India to adopt belligerent foreign policy against Pakistan. “The tensions between India and its neighboring countries indicates that American support to India has encouraged the latter to adopt aggressive attitude towards its neighboring countries, particularly Pakistan.” (Imran. S, interview 15-09-2021).

India and the United States has signed a number of agreements and deals in order to cement their bilateral relations. Coupled with serving American interests, these deals have given India an edge over its rivals, particularly Pakistan. “The US has ignored Pakistan while establishing its relations with India”. (G. Ali, interview 16-09-2021). Thus, Pakistan become less important for the United States and was replaced with India as ally of the United State in South Asia region. In post 9/11 era, India replaced Pakistan as strategic partner of the United States in the South Asia region. Though Pakistan was non-NATO ally of the United States on war on terror, India appeared to be more important for her in 21st century. “Regional environment after 9/11 compelled the United States to flourish strong ties with India. The US believed that Pakistan is not doing enough to punish the culprits of 9/11. It kept demanding “do more”. Therefore, the US found India trustworthy friendly state in South Asia region.” (Imran, interview 15-09-2021).

India and the United States signed Civil Nuclear Deal in 2005 which strengthen their strategic partnership. The deal enables India to buy conventional weapons from the United States. The Indo-US Nuclear Deal gave birth to security concerns for regional countries in general and Pakistan in particular. The agreement enabled to make pre-emptive attacks on Pakistan. In addition, Pakistan faced adverse implications when India and the United States signed The Logistic Exchange Memorandum of Agreement (LEMOA) in 2016. “The LEMOA also helps the militaries of the two sides to coordinate better and take interoperability in bilateral exercises to the next level.” (Mishra, 2018).

The agreement had deep implications for Pakistan as it had widen disparity between military

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of two countries. Furthermore, the LEMOA agreement was signed by the two countries during turbulence in Indian Illegally Occupied Jammu & Kashmir. Signing of agreement with India in that situation shows that the United States considers bilateral issue between the two countries. Pakistan feels uneasy due to America's "willingness to make concessions to India on Kashmir." (Basrur, 2009). Thus, Islamabad has lost a major actor through which New Delhi could be influenced to find a peaceful solution to the issue. "It has increased international support for India on Kashmir, Afghanistan and terrorism issue that is major concerns of Pakistan." (Khusboo, interview 13-09-2021). Apart from that, many experts believed in Pakistan that the agreement could also damage China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) projects.

The United States and India in October 2020 signed Basic Exchange Cooperation Agreement (BECA) which also gave birth to security concerns for Pakistan as it would destabilize the South Asia region. Though the deal aims to contain China but Pakistan fears that it would damage its security as India would use advanced technologies for accessing to its classified military intelligence. In addition, Pakistan shares anxiety that the United States is improving India's nuclear weapon program which would disturb the balance of power in the region.

Indo-US strategic partnership further fortified with the signing of the foundational agreements. These agreements benefit India as she receives technological and technical information and systems. Furthermore, the agreements enable India to buy top American weapons systems which ultimately increases its power against neighboring states, particularly Pakistan and China. The foundational agreements enhances India's military capability and helps her to achieve its ambitions of becoming regional power.

Pakistan perceives strategic cooperation between India and the United States as threat to her territorial integrity and sovereignty. The United States wants to contain China through India. Whereas India has more ambitions other than preventing the rise of China. With the increase in military and conventional capabilities, India's desire for regional dominance has also increased. Moreover, India's access to United States' advanced weapons will also adversely affect Pakistan's security. "The US has ignored Pakistan while establishing its relations with India." (G. Ali, interview 16-09-2021).

Moreover, Indo-US maritime cooperation under their strategic partnership is, in fact, aimed at securing maritime domain that would ultimately give birth to serious maritime conflicts between India and Pakistan in the Indian Ocean Region (IOR) and international seas. The Indo-US Malabar series of naval exercises have arisen as a key component in of their maritime partnership (Rani, 2013). The neighboring countries of India, especially Pakistan, have shown serious concerns over America's support to India. In addition, New Delhi has amplified military exercises with Indo-Pacific states (Zakharov, 2019). It seems that the United States has allowed and emboldened India to play key role in Indo-Pacific region. India has been recognized by the US as a security provider in the Indian Ocean Region (Rani, 2013).

The export control wavier given to India has not only brought two countries close to each other but has also helped India to boost its domestic defense industries to fulfil its "Make in India" dream. "Make in India" is national program of the Indian government designated to facilitate to protect intellectual property, investment, enhance development skill and build best in class manufacturing infrastructure in the country. Thus, to attract investment from

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across the globe and strengthening India's manufacturing sector are major objectives of the initiative. Therefore, it will further exacerbate the existing imbalance between India and Pakistan.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The United States foreign policy has tilted towards India. The two countries have signed a number of bilateral agreements or deals. These deals strengthen India's military and defense capability. Simultaneously, the agreements also protect and promote the United States' interests in the region. The investigation has revealed that India wants access to American modern weapons and technology. While the United States want to contain the rising influence of China. India wants to give practical shape to her hegemonic designs with the help of the United States. Meanwhile, Pakistan perceives strategic cooperation between India and the United as threat to its territorial integrity and sovereignty. The study suggests that Pakistan ought to make its foreign policy consistent in order to counter the growing ties of India and the US. Foreign policy ought to be shaped for at least 10 years. Governments may change but foreign policy should be same. It will make foreign policy effective and will help her achieve its long term objectives.

Besides, International public opinion regarding Pakistan has not been positive. Pakistan direly needs to leverage international public opinion in its favor. Foreign policy makers should strive hard to project an image of Pakistan as democratic and liberal state. Moreover, Pakistan should strengthen its diplomatic ties with European Union, Russia, the U.S and other important countries. Pakistan should stop relying on only specific country. Simultaneously, Pakistan should make efforts for the revival of Organization of Islam Cooperation. The OIC can potentially pressurize India to resolve outstanding issues with Pakistan. Additionally, Pakistan should improve its relations with neighboring countries particularly with Iran and Afghanistan. Friendly relations with Iran will ensure that its soil will not be used against Pakistan. Iran's energy resources will fulfill Pakistan's domestic as well as industrial needs. Similarly, affable government in Afghanistan would also bar India from using its soil against Pakistan. Moreover, Pakistan and China should ensure the completion of projects under CPEC on time. Completion of the projects will provide strategical and economic benefits to Pakistan. It should also invite other countries, including, Russia, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Afghanistan, and CARs, to join CPEC. Their participation will also strengthen Pakistan's economic and strategic position.

References

1. Basrur Rajesh M. (2009). Nuclear Weapons and India-Pakistan Relations. Strategic Analysis. P 342
2. Bishoyi Saroj. (2011). Defense Diplomacy in Indo-US Strategic Relationship. Journal of Defence Studies, Vol 5. No 1. P.75
3. Mistry, D. (2020). Divergence and convergence in US-Pakistan security relations. Asian Security, 16(2), 243-262.
4. Interview was taken through email from Bilveer Singh, dated: 18-09-2021
5. Interview was taken through email from Khushboo Ejaz, dated: 13-09-2021
6. Interview was taken through email from Imran Sandano, dated: 15-09-2021
7. Interview was taken through email from Ayesha, dated: 22-09-2021

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8. Interview was taken through email from Ghulam Ali, dated: 16-09-2021
9. Iqbal, Asma (2020). Indo –US Strategic Partnership and Its Fall Outs on Pakistan. *Journal of Politics and International Studies*.
10. Jr. David W. Kearns. (2014). *Toward Alliance or Ambivalence: A Theoretical Assessment of U.S.-India Relations*. *India Review*. P 134.
11. Kaura, V. (2019). Incorporating Indo-Pacific and the Quadrilateral into India's strategic outlook. *Maritime Affairs: Journal of the National Maritime Foundation of India*, 15(2), 78-102.
12. Konwer Shubhrajeev. (2020). *US-India Relations: The Shadowboxing Era*. *Strategic Analysis*. P.19
13. Kronstadt, K. A., & Pinto, S. (2013). *US-India Security Relations: Strategic Issues*. Congressional Research Service,
14. Markey, D. S. (2013). *No exit from Pakistan: America's tortured relationship with Islamabad*. Cambridge University Press.
15. Mishra Vivek. (2018). *India-US Defence Cooperation: Assessing Strategic Imperatives*. *Strategic Analysis*. P. 11
16. Owais, Muhammad (2020). "Indian Ocean and Indo-China Rivalry: Challenges for Pakistan" *Journal of Indian Studies*. Vol. 6, No. 1, P. 92
17. Rani Sudesh. (2013). *Indo-US Maritime Cooperation: Challenges and Prospects*. *Maritime Affairs*. P.126
18. Shah, S. N. A., & Majeed, G. (2019). *Deconstructing the Problematic Relationship of Pakistan and United States of America: Challenges and Opportunities for Pakistan*. *Journal of Political Studies*, 26(2).
19. Upadhyay, S. (2014). *The Indo-Pacific & the Indo-US Relations: Geopolitics of Cooperation*. Institute of Peace and Conflict Studies (IPCS).
20. Zakharov Aleksei. (2019). *The Geopolitics of the US-India-Russia Strategic Triangle*. *Strategic Analysis*. P. 362